

WAYS OF IMPROVING THE ADMINISTRATIVE-LEGAL MECHANISMS OF ENSURING ROAD TRAFFIC SAFETY

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Abstract: In this article, the main goal of reforms implemented in the field of road safety is to strengthen legal guarantees to protect the life and health of road users. In this regard, the importance of developing new and modern mechanisms for ensuring road safety, conducting scientific research in these areas of activity, developing effective research methods and solving problems was discussed.

Key words: Road, security, administrative-legal, foreign, international, global, expanded, motor transport

Ensuring road safety remains one of the most urgent problems in the 21st century. The meetings of the UN General Assembly and the decisions adopted in it also show that the world community takes a serious approach to solving this problem.

There are many examples of effective international cooperation in the field of traffic management and the use of innovations in this field. International legal mechanisms are an important part of the process of standardization and harmonization of legislation of different countries in the field of transport. Therefore, all international organizations note the need to strengthen the rule of law on roads and improve the quality of highways.

About 50 million people are injured and more than 1 million people die in road traffic accidents worldwide every year. According to the World Health Organization, Ethiopia ranks first and Uganda ranks second in the number of deaths due to road traffic accidents.

Road accidents are one of the top ten causes of disability. The total cost of economic damage is 500 billion US dollars per year. Some foreign countries have achieved certain results in terms of road safety, reducing the number of road deaths compared to other countries. Effective use of foreign best practice serves to ensure road safety, reduce the level of road traffic accidents, protect the rights of road users, and improve public administration in this area[1].

Studying advanced foreign experience in road safety and introducing it into our national legal system is one of the priority ways to further improve the legal basis of activities in the field of road safety. At the same time, direct assimilation of foreign experience is not effective enough, as a result, it may cause contradictions in legislation, gaps in the regulation of one or another type of legal relations. It is also important to take into account the national traditions and trends in the field of law-making, along with the adoption of positive experience [2].

A. V. Porublen said that most accidents occur in countries around Africa and the Mediterranean Sea. It is there that there are no necessary laws to punish drunk drivers, set a certain speed on the roads, and oblige them to wear seat belts [3].

It has been scientifically proven that by 2030, more people will die from road traffic accidents than from diseases if appropriate measures are not taken. At the same time, the state of road safety is much higher in countries where this problem is given importance at the state level. The roads of the following countries are considered safe: Malta (33 deaths per 1 million population), the Netherlands (49 deaths per 1 million population), Sweden, Norway, Great Britain, Switzerland, Germany, Finland, Denmark, Japan and Iceland (per 1 million population 79 deaths).

International legal norms and institutional mechanisms for the implementation of administrative-legal mechanisms for ensuring traffic safety within the framework of this paragraph: 1) advanced experience of the most developed countries and countries on the path to development, in particular, liability for violations of traffic rules; 2) public control in determining these violations; 3) a number of issues, such as improvement of legislation in this regard, are studied from a comparative legal point of view.

1. International-legal norms and institutional mechanisms for the provision of EHS. In order to solve problems related to road safety, legal and institutional mechanisms that serve to reduce the number of road traffic accidents have been developed by the world community. The UN is of particular importance in solving this problem.

Today, two international conventions in the field of traffic have entered into force under the auspices of the UN, which are the Convention on Road Signs and Signals, signed in Geneva on March 1, 1973, which describes the purpose of all road signs and specifies the rules for their installation, and the Convention on Road Traffic, which entered into force on May 21, 1977.

Also, the resolution 64/255 adopted by the UN General Assembly in March 2010 states the following as the main risk factors leading to traffic accidents: firstly, the lack or non-use of safety devices for children; secondly, not using protective equipment; thirdly, driving a car under the influence of alcohol or drugs; fourth, exceeding the permitted speed of movement or moving at a speed that does not correspond to the road conditions; fifth, insufficient infrastructure[4].

Despite the fact that the resolution has a recommendatory nature, it is mentioned to take measures against factors that distract from driving, in particular, talking on the phone while driving, and sending SMS messages, which lead to emergency situations.

The next important event of the UN activities in this direction is the adoption by the General Assembly of April 4, 2012 resolution No. 66/368 on improving road safety around the world. This resolution was signed by about 50 countries. It also involves the activation of activities in the field of road safety and the strengthening of political freedom to ensure road safety, including the development of international legal documents, including safety-related international conventions and agreements, technical standards, resolutions and recommendations, regional and national tasks to reduce injuries from road traffic accidents are defined at the level. At the same time, the resolution provides information on road safety in low- and middle-income countries.

Currently, many countries of the world are managing to put road safety on the global political agenda. The World Health Organization, the World Bank and the European Union have recently developed comprehensive road safety plans.

International road death rates allow any country to compare with other countries, taking into account different levels of population, vehicles and distances traveled. Although these indicators and rankings change every year, some countries have consistently shown better road safety performance than others.

Resolutions adopted by the UN General Assembly called on the world community to modernize and improve road accident data collection systems, to invest in road accident monitoring and analysis programs, and to collect new information from consumers around the world about the safety, comfort and reliability of vehicles, calls for testing vehicles, improving the quality of primary inpatient care and medical care (allocating a special number to an ambulance, providing doctors with the necessary equipment).

2. Liability for traffic violations. Liability for traffic offenses has its own characteristics in different countries. During the analysis of the legislation in the field of traffic safety in foreign countries, it was found that the main focus of punishment is on the financial responsibility of traffic violators, but this applies not only to large fines, but also to the confiscation of motor vehicles, the deprivation of a driver's license, the seriousness and amount of the violation are linked to the mandatory annual car insurance.

Fines for traffic violations vary not only depending on the monthly wage or minimum wage set by the country, but also based on the annual tax-free income of the violator. If the offender does not pay the fine within 1 month from the date of violation, the amount of the fine may increase.

Recently, the legislators in Europe and the world are on the way to strengthen responsibility for traffic violations. In some countries, such methods are showing positive results and the number of road deaths has decreased significantly.

According to legal scientist S.A. Guseynov, in addition to legal promotion and legal enforcement, the tasks of changing the entire road infrastructure (building roads and cars, modern road traffic, improving technical and other culture in this area) are also important. As for legal means, all legal work should be done not in the direction of prohibition and increasing responsibility, but also in the field of creating conditions that maximally encourage the legal behavior of road users. At the same time, it is necessary to create conditions in which accident-free operation is economically beneficial and encouraged in every way[5].

For example, in Belgium, Israel, Spain and the USA, if the fine is not paid, the car will be impounded with bail or a fine for parking. In Japan, driving license suspension is provided for this violation. In Germany, for example, the amount of insurance is increased according to the accumulated penalty points for traffic violations. If the insurance amount is one hundred euros, it will be increased by another 500 euros, for the second year - by 1000 euros, and so on. Therefore, often many violators prefer not to use the car for the whole year in order not to pay three times the cost of insurance later.

In Great Britain, the system of penalty points for traffic offenses is implemented on the basis of the Road Traffic Offenders Act of 1988. In accordance with Annex 2 of the Act, separate points are determined for certain offenses. The driver's license of a driver or motorcyclist who has accumulated 12 or more points over three years is compulsorily

revoked. Also, separate penalty points are set for some crimes. In this case, the court has the right to deprive the offender of the right to drive a vehicle.

In Portugal, the point system for recording violations was introduced from June 1, 2016. The peculiarity of this system is that drivers are immediately awarded 12 points. In case of violation of traffic rules (from 2 to 6 depending on the severity of the violation), the corresponding points are "removed". After reaching a certain number of points, the driver is obliged to take training courses or his right to drive a car is revoked. It is assumed that points can be collected for the absence of violations (maximum amount - up to 15 points).

The form of administration in the USA determines the existence of different forms of legal regulation of administrative responsibility in the field of traffic in different states. For example, the state of Missouri has a point system used to record offenses. The amount of points depends on the type of traffic violation. For example, when the speed limit is exceeded, the driver may receive 2 or 3 points for this case, or the driver may receive 12 points for failure to perform his duty due to a traffic accident, and at the same time be deprived of the right to drive a vehicle. The number of points that cause drivers to be deprived of the right to drive a vehicle is set from 12 to 24. In addition, information about accumulated points can be obtained for free from the public database on the website of the Missouri Department of Transportation.

Calculation of penalty points for traffic violations is also carried out in Australia, Germany, Israel, Italy, Latvia, South Korea and a number of other countries. Many CIS countries are also considering the possibility of introducing a point system. For example, in Belarus, a draft law is being discussed, which provides for the calculation of penalty points for "administrative offenses related to the use of transport by traffic safety, or when an administrative process is being conducted by internal affairs bodies against a person driving a vehicle or a decision to impose an administrative penalty."

In Moldova, the Code of Offenses is in force, in which a special type of administrative punishment is of interest - the awarding of points for the committed administrative offenses. Their number depends on the seriousness of the act and the risk to the public (from 2 to 6 points). At the same time, if an individual has accumulated more than 15 penalty points, in the case of the next offense, the case will be sent to the court, which will impose the deprivation of the right to drive a vehicle for a period of 6 months to 1 year as an additional punishment. 2004 years in Latvia and Norway,

In 2005 years, Мальтада, in 2006 years Spain and Romania introduced a point system for administrative offenses. According to statistics, the number of people injured and killed in traffic accidents in these countries is constantly decreasing.

In our opinion, speeding is another reason for the high number of deaths and injuries on the roads. For example, in Australia and New Zealand, the maximum speed allowed in populated areas is 50 km per hour, even a minimum exceeding of this speed (for example, 5 km per hour) is an administrative offense and leads to administrative liability. Similar rules apply in a number of other foreign countries, such as Turkey and EU countries.

In many countries, a fine is provided for exceeding the maximum permitted speed by at least 10 km per hour. In Norway, it is an offense to increase the speed by 5 km/h, and in the Netherlands by 4 km/h. In addition, in Germany, France, the Czech Republic and Sweden, fines for speeding in built-up areas are much higher than outside built-up areas. This will help to

reduce the number of traffic accidents that occur mainly in residential areas and reduce the number of deaths and injuries faced by road users[6].

In addition to speeding, factors such as driving under the influence of drugs also contribute to the increase in traffic deaths. At the same time, according to the traffic rules, it is forbidden to transfer the vehicle to a sick or other person who is under the influence of drugs that weaken the reaction and attention, who threatens the safety of movement. In this regard, the experience of Sweden can be a positive example, there.

In 1997, the parliament approved a new road safety program, "Target Zero", in which all organizations connected to the road system in one way or another in Sweden define tasks and other performance standards based on social partnership. The ultimate goal of this program is to ensure that there are no deaths or serious injuries from traffic accidents. It is based on the concept of public health care. The "Target Zero" program has a long-term strategy and aims to gradually improve road safety until the set goal is reached.

This program promotes shared responsibility and flexibility to redistribute responsibility to the extent that science and experience define the optimal roles of the automotive industry, traffic planners, safety engineers, law enforcement and health officials, educators, and road users. For example, if it is not possible to significantly improve the safety of cars and roads, more attention should be paid to reducing speed. Conversely, if further reductions in speed are not desirable, greater emphasis can be placed on improving vehicle and road safety.

In European law, there are also types of offenses such as "aggression on the road" (aggressive driving). However, it is very difficult to clearly define its boundaries and forms.

According to the results of a sociological survey of the European population conducted by the Gellap Institute, the most aggressive offense on our continent is "aggressive flashing of car lights". In Australia, this is an offense of disorderly gestures, while in Japan, it is "aggressive pursuit", i.e., following another vehicle at too close a distance[6].

The meaning of this term is debated all over the world. An informal conference held in Canada addressed the same problem, and provided an understanding that a driver's behavior is considered aggressive if it intentionally increases the risk of a collision, or if it is related to irritation, intentional conflict.

Usually, road aggression means violation of several rules at the same time (violation of maneuvering rules, overtaking vehicles standing on a congested road from the opposite lane, driving off the side of the road, on the sidewalk). In this case, the driver shows disrespect to other road users.

The penalty for this offense is set much higher than for other violations. In Germany, Denmark, Latvia and other countries, if this offense is repeated, the driver's license will be revoked for up to one year.

European Union traffic regulations have introduced sanctions for not complying with the flow distance. For example, if a car coming from behind at a speed of 100 km / h approaches the car in front less than 15 meters, the driver of the second car will be fined 150 euros. In addition, the German Penal Code stipulates a three-month driving license suspension and a 250-euro fine for overtaking. If these actions lead to more serious consequences, the punishment of imprisonment for 5 years is prescribed. In the US, the New York police have the right to impound cars from drivers who behave dangerously and aggressively on the road.

The Traffic Safety Policy Act in Japan requires the government to report annually on the status of traffic accidents, measures taken, and plans for traffic safety. Every five years, the Expert Panels develop the main programs of Road Safety.

Safer new road construction and reconstruction has been introduced in Japan. As a result, the road network with a low accident rate is constantly expanding. According to the new regulation, first of all, a set of target indicators for reducing accidents is determined, and then the types of countermeasures necessary to achieve these targets are selected. The level of achievement of the target is evaluated annually.

"Safe Pedestrian Areas" have been identified and become the focus of area-wide traffic accident prevention measures (restricting traffic, warning drivers about road features, and delineating traffic and pedestrian areas). Wide sidewalks are also being built around school routes, train stations, and other public facilities.

Japan is trying to eliminate utility poles and build pedestrian overpasses with elevators, establish pedestrian rest areas, build bicycle parking lots, and do a number of things to make signs and symbols more visible to the elderly.

Japan implements the Generation Exchange Project, where three generations meet to learn about road safety, and the Home Visiting Project, which provides traffic safety guidance at home to seniors who cannot attend seminars. Road safety clubs are organized in old people's clubs and nursing homes. Training for drivers between the ages of 65 and 70 teaches changes in their physical activity, driving tendencies and the characteristics of the accidents they are most likely to encounter.

Japan has stepped up calls for pedestrians to use reflective materials as a means of preventing pedestrian accidents at night. Prefectural police distributed reflective materials on street corners, at nursing home visits and at educational events. Night programs are being implemented to increase public awareness of the benefits of wearing reflective material. Fashion items feature highlighted reflective materials, including footwear and accessories. The number of people who wear reflective material every time they leave home at night rose from 23 percent to 35 percent.

In Japan, the Medics in Helicopters program, which uses specially equipped helicopters and has a doctor on board, aims to provide better medical care in emergencies and during patient transport. By the end of 2005, ten emergency stations in nine prefectures were using such helicopters. To improve pre-hospital care, the government also encourages the use of medic vehicles (ambulances with a doctor on board) and trains emergency life-saving technicians to achieve systematic deployment of such personnel.

In our opinion, the point system for recording violations of traffic rules is aimed at depriving the driver of the right to drive a vehicle in cases where the sanction for a specific offense does not provide for such a punishment. In addition, this system is significant in that it requires the driver to attend special paid courses on traffic rules. The point system of recording cases of violations of traffic rules, which has been in force in foreign countries for a long time, has been showing its effectiveness. In this regard, we believe that the following issues should be resolved in order to assess the possibility of introducing one or another version of the point system for recording violations from Uzbekistan:

first, classification of violations according to the level of seriousness and assigning corresponding "penalty" points;

secondly, scientific-theoretical justification of the essence of the measure of deprivation of the right to drive a vehicle as an administrative punishment measure and as an administrative precautionary (restriction) measure;

thirdly, to determine the possibility of the driver of a vehicle to study in special mandatory training courses for the restoration of the right to drive a vehicle.

3. Public control in the detection of violations in the field of providing health care. Illegal and dangerous behavior of road users, especially drivers, is one of the main causes of accidents in all countries of the world. Therefore, it is very necessary to raise the legal awareness of citizens in this regard. At the same time, the involvement of the public in such activities is a common practice in many countries, has been implemented for a long time, and, of course, is characterized by high efficiency.

For example, a special "SpotSquad" program for smartphones was developed and tested in Canada. This application allows you to record the fact of violation of parking rules and automatically send the data to the city parking control or the police. At the same time, this application specifies the geographical coordinates of the place where the offense was committed, as well as the exact time of recording it. A person who reports a parking violation will begin receiving a financial reward of 10 percent of the amount of the fine imposed on the offender after three confirmed reports. As the number of confirmed messages increases, the salary increases and can reach up to 40% of the fine.

Singapore is one of the bright representatives of Asian countries. Singapore is often called an "economic miracle", which allows it to be included among the most developed countries. Despite the occupied area (725 sq. km), as well as the population (more than 5.5 million), Singapore has a highly developed transport infrastructure. The total length of road networks in this country is 3250 km, including 161 km of highways.

In Singapore, there is a special form on the official Internet resources of the police, through which to report a traffic violation, a brief description of the situation and the time of occurrence must be indicated, indicating the applicant's personal information. To confirm the authenticity of the entered data, the following files are attached: Singapore citizen's passport photo and photo or video material[8].

A special mobile application was created in South Korea, and the development of the program aimed not only to provide law enforcement agencies with the opportunity to immediately report the fact of a crime, but also to organize feedback. This implies the possibility to determine the status of the complaint, as well as the results of its review, through the chat included in the application. The program and the service it provides are very popular. Within a year after its implementation, about half a million appeals were received from interested citizens.

In our opinion, taking into account the high dynamics of social processes and the optimization of the activities of internal affairs bodies, it is necessary to recognize the importance of the public. In many countries (especially in Sweden[9]), the participation of persons with an active civil position in ensuring road traffic safety is exposed in some organizational and legal forms, which allows to increase their responsibility in fulfilling their civic duty and to apply incentive measures.

4. Improvement of the legislation in the field of providing health care. Most developed countries are trying to solve the problem through strict legal regulation. These countries systematically develop and adopt important regulatory documents at various levels. The most common codes contain generalized norms that regulate all elements of the road safety system.

In particular, in the countries of Israel, Brazil, and the Czech Republic, such relations are regulated by the Road Codes. The rules that ensure road safety in France consist of 5 volumes. They cover traffic rules and regulations. It also contains a set of various instructions on road safety rules, signs and signals.

Traffic in Germany is regulated by several legal documents, "On Traffic Safety", "On Violation of Traffic Rules", "On Traffic Rules". According to them, fines are detailed in a special catalog. This allows not only to correctly classify violations, but also to encourage drivers to follow traffic rules.

Legislators of a number of European countries believe that road safety can be more effectively regulated by separate laws. For example, in Sweden, regulatory documents have been developed and adopted that specifically regulate issues such as traffic violations, driver training and driver's license revocation, driving school regulations, parking rules, and transportation of dangerous goods. According to them, the norms contained in separate laws regulate almost all traffic situations that occur during the use of vehicles, and the accuracy is high.

Therefore, Estonia followed suit, where public and freight transport laws were passed, as well as a road law. On administrative offenses, separate laws on transport insurance define responsibilities according to their content. Some countries have limited themselves only to the adoption of traffic rules. In this case, separate legal documents regulate the rules of vehicle registration, placement of road signs and their use. Driving of heavy goods vehicles, training and licensing of drivers and other measures related to road safety are also specified in separate laws.

Azerbaijan, Italy, China and Japan have adopted traffic laws and traffic rules are an integral part of these regulations. In many countries, traffic rules are adopted at the legislative level and operated independently. In addition to them, traffic rules are also applied. Countries where road traffic and its safety are regulated by law include Great Britain, Hungary, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, and Lithuania.

A number of countries have formed a legal framework regulating road traffic safety and developed special legal documents to ensure safety. Such a law exists, for example, in Spain and is called the "Basic Law on Motor Traffic and Road Safety". Road safety issues in Norway are regulated by the Road Traffic Act. Bulgaria, Denmark, Ukraine, Finland have a single law that regulates all areas of road safety.

Differences in the approaches of legislators in a particular country will depend on the national characteristics of the law-making process, the requirements of constitutional principles and the mentality of those nations. A common feature in the legislation of all countries is that material liability is the main means of influence in them. They are mainly manifested in three areas: first, the progressive and full scale of fines; second, encourage violators to pay their annual car insurance; thirdly, confiscation of motor vehicles.

The practice of driving license suspension is also widespread, and law enforcement agencies strive to make full use of the principle of the inevitability of punishment.

A study of the experience of foreign countries in creating a road safety system shows that the work in this regard is carried out more effectively in countries that have created national programs for the implementation of this problem. National road safety programs include a set of activities, identify appropriate resources, and provide deadlines for the implementation of expected results.

The analysis of the international experience in the development of national programs to ensure road safety allows us to distinguish some principles of this activity: first, to create institutions that work on the constant control over the causes of accidents, to identify the situations that lead to road traffic accidents; secondly, to establish programs of socio-economic measures that apply to all subjects of road traffic; thirdly, the programs of the countries under study have sections on the implementation dates and their results; fourthly, the programs are constantly corrected and supplemented (this is due to changes in the socio-economic situation and the development of scientific and technical progress).

Australia, Austria, Bulgaria, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Denmark, Spain, Italy, Canada and other countries have adopted national road safety programs. The experience of creating national programs in these countries requires further study. Some of the positive aspects of these programs would be adapted in the life of our country.

In some countries, national road safety programs are an integral part of the state's national safety programs. This increases the possibility of solving traffic safety problems. For example, in Great Britain, the program "Future Roads Safe for All" was adopted as an independent document. Later, this document was included in the "Future of Transport", a national strategy for the development of transport in the period until 2030[10].

National road safety programs are sometimes supplemented by special programs aimed at improving one or another element of the road safety system. As a rule, this is done within the framework of programs under the conditional name of "safe city". In this regard, the Republic of Korea, which has a program called "intelligent transport system" based on the use of digital technologies, can be a clear example.

In a number of European countries, national programs are adopted by parliaments or, after approval by the parliament, the program is signed by the country's president. In most countries, programs are issued by government decree or approved by relevant ministries and approved by the legislature. The most striking example is Sweden, where the national plan for the development of the road transport system includes sections on road safety. The country has a "National Road Safety Coordination Forum" that coordinates the activities of all subjects of this field and monitors its implementation. A special section of the document provides for the regulation and development of roads and street networks. It is noteworthy that the financing of national programs is carried out at the expense of the state budget.

Finland currently has an advisory committee on road safety. Under his leadership, the national road safety program approved by the Ministry of Transport and Communications Development was developed. The program includes 50 courses. Each direction has its own managers[11].

Several programs are underway in the Netherlands. Among them, the mobility plan aimed at ensuring road safety stands out. The advantage of this document is that it coordinates the activities of state authorities, local government authorities, public organizations.

In Japan, together with the General Police Department for Public Safety, there is a state commission that develops programs and measures to ensure traffic safety. Programs created by this commission include a complex of state-wide measures.

The study of legal documents ensuring road safety in foreign countries confirms that, regardless of existing economic relations and political structures, the task of ensuring road safety is solved at the state level. Most countries have adopted relevant codes or national

programs. The normative legal framework in the field of traffic safety is based on the constitutional principles in force in a particular country, as well as the customs and mentality of the population, and the general legal culture.

Each country strives to create fundamental legal documents that ensure public safety in traffic conditions. Priority will be given to the programs provided with high technologies of monitoring, control and analysis, improvement of socio-economic conditions, carrying out propaganda work with the population. The priority areas that ensure road safety in different countries are:

first, compliance with traffic rules (promoting the culture of behavior on the roads, raising legal consciousness, putting a firm end to legal nihilism, controlling the behavior of drivers and pedestrians on the roads, fighting against drunkenness). Based on this experience, we recommend studying the special subject of safe behavior on the road in the primary program of compulsory primary education for children aged 6 to 12 years in our country's schools. During the secondary school years (12-16 young), minors must complete a second compulsory education program in the same subject, but with in-depth knowledge, and pass two compulsory theoretical exams, first at the age of 12 and then at the age of 15. After successfully passing this theoretical exam, the student gets the right to drive a moped, which can be done after passing special practical training and a practical exam. Only then will it be possible to study at a driving school for the possibility of having the right to drive a passenger vehicle;

secondly, technical improvement of motor vehicles (improvement of structures, warning equipment, safety systems);

thirdly, creating a safe road environment (safe city systems, controlling the issuance of driver's licenses, improving the quality of education and improving the skills of drivers);

fourth, improving the provision of medical assistance in traffic accidents;

fifth, to increase the responsibility of persons who commit offenses in the course of traffic.

The conclusion from the above is that it is important for each country to develop and implement its own road safety policy. In our opinion, it is time to introduce a penalty points system. After all, the purpose of the point system is to identify and prevent drivers who have committed the most serious administrative offenses in the field of traffic or who violate traffic rules more often than other drivers.

A modern system of penalty points may include: five-level points; compliance with the severity of the offense, the amount of the fine and the number of accumulated negative points; exclusion of many offenses from the system of penalty points - mostly light ones; the impossibility of canceling points on administrative offenses with a serious public risk using a corrective tool; extending the correction tools and adapting it to the driver.

At the same time, despite various efforts, the number of road traffic accidents and victims in our country remains much higher than in many European countries. Therefore, it is necessary to study their methods and tools in the fight against traffic injuries and apply the experience they have gained in our country. It is necessary to pay special attention not only to the legislation of foreign countries, but also to the methods of preventing traffic accidents in them.

Road safety policies are more aimed at reducing the number of casualties. It is necessary to popularize the philosophy of "protecting people first".

In this context, issues of road safety in foreign countries are resolved through research on the regulatory legal documents regulating traffic rules, determining responsibility for violations, as well as applying standards related to this field.

There are many differences between countries, including cultural, legal requirements, road network standards, use of different modes of travel, etc. Implementation and implementation of "foreign" solutions can be successful only after careful consideration of these issues.

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